

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF FINANCING THE SOCIAL SECTOR ON THE BASIS OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK ASOSIDA IJTIMOYIY SOHANI MOLIALASHTIRISHNING AMALDAGI MEXANIZMLARI TAHLILI

¹Khalilova Shokhsanam Gayrat qizi

¹PhD, Tashkent State University of Economics, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.
G-mail: shoxsanamhalilova@gmail.com

Annotation
Annotatsiya

Eng. - This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of public-private partnerships (PPPs). Social welfare is defined as the main criterion for assessing the social significance of PPPs. The study identifies the objectives of private sector partners and the government, and evaluates the practical outcomes of PPPs based on social welfare indicators. By comparing the existing outcomes with the expected social effects, recommendations are developed for governments on the formation of PPP institutions and their effective management. The findings show that applying these recommendations may reduce the number of PPP projects, bring them closer to traditional government contracts, and increase the opportunities for improving social welfare.

Uzb. - Ushbu maqolada davlat-xususiy sheriklik (DXSh)ning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari tahlil etiladi. DXShning ijtimoiy ahamiyatini baholashda ijtimoiy farovonlik mezonini asosiy ko'rsatkich sifatida belgilanadi. Tadqiqotda xususiy sektor hamkorlari va davlatning maqsadlari aniqlashtiriladi hamda DXShning amaliy natijalari ijtimoiy farovonlik mezonlari asosida baholanadi. Mavjud natijalar bilan kutilgan ijtimoiy samaralar taqqoslanib, DXSh institutlarini shakllantirish va ularni samarali boshqarish bo'yicha amaliyot uchun tavsiyalar ishlab chiqiladi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, tavsiyalarni qo'llash orqali DXSh loyihalari soni kamayishi, ular an'anaviy davlat shartnomalariga yaqinlashishi va ijtimoiy farovonlikni oshirish imkoniyatlari ortishi mumkin.

Keywords:
Kalit so'zlar:

❖ *public-private partnership, infrastructure, project, investment, priority national segments, sustainability.*

❖ *davlat-xususiy sheriklik (DXSh), infratuzilma, loyiha, investitsiya, ustuvor milliy yo'nalishlar, barqarorlik.*

Introduction.

Today, in the development of the country, the issue of development of human intellectual capital, accumulation of scientific and technical potential and provision of their use, informatization of all spheres of activity is very urgent and important. Projects and programs aimed at abstracting human labor and replacing it with machine labor are being developed. In order for any country to achieve development, it is necessary and necessary to

introduce digital knowledge and modern information technologies. This gives the opportunity to take the shortest path to ascension. Currently, information technologies are deeply penetrating all spheres of human life and activity.

Although the digital economy is a relatively new concept, many definitions have been given to it by experts. Summarizing these definitions allows us to define it as follows: Digital economy is an economic activity based

on digital technologies, connected to e-business, e-commerce, producing and providing digital goods and services. In this case, payments for economic services and goods are made through electronic money [1]. It should be noted that digital technologies will dramatically change more than 50 percent of the economy-related sectors. The digital economy is not just one type of activity, but also business, industrial facilities, quality education and services. The term "digital" refers to the active use of information technologies in all areas. If in the ordinary economy material goods are considered the main resource, in the digital economy it will be information and data that can be processed and transmitted. After their analysis, a proper management solution is developed [2]. In the modern sense, the partnership between the state and business is an institutional and organizational alliance between the state and private companies, banks, international financial organizations, and other institutions in order to implement socially significant projects. The nature of this interaction, methods and specific forms may vary significantly depending on the maturity and national characteristics of market relations. At the same time, the state is never free from fulfilling its socially responsible functions related to national interests, and business, in turn, always remains the source and accelerator of the process, the increment of social wealth.

Today, systematic work is being carried out to develop the preschool education system of Uzbekistan based on innovative technologies, to improve the national education system, to educate young people based on information and communication technologies, to modernize higher education institutions, and to introduce the latest achievements of foreign educational institutions to them. Five priority directions of the action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan were adopted, and in its fourth social sector

development section, special attention was paid to the development of education and science.

Research methodology.

Theoretical methods: comparative analysis of psychological, pedagogical and scientific-methodological literature, normative, methodological and legal documents on research issues, methodological analysis of the professional and federal state. Educational standards of higher education; analysis and generalization of foreign and local experience; Pedagogical modeling of the personalized educational process and forecasting of its results; comparing, systematizing and summarizing information. Empirical research methods: pedagogical observation, questioning, survey, test, monitoring, mutual control, self-evaluation, mutual evaluation, interview with the teacher and students, diagnostics of the level of formation of educational results, pedagogical experiment. Statistical methods of research data processing: statistical data collection, rating, scaling, rating evaluation, mathematical statistics methods for processing the results of pedagogical research.

Analysis and discussion of results.

What needs to be done to effectively use digital technologies in education and early childhood education while maintaining the quality of teaching?. First of all, we must improve the Internet infrastructure in our country, increase the quality of services provided by mobile operators, and most importantly, create conditions and privileges for the population, especially students and young people, to master the latest achievements of modern information and communication technologies.

Secondly, to expand the scope of use of digital technologies in the organization of the educational process and to develop information resources, teaching tools and distance learning technologies, to involve creative students in university digitization projects, to make proposals to the competent authorities on

making changes to the regulatory legal documents regulating the activities of higher education institutions, high organization of centers, including structures equipped with effective digital devices, classrooms, laboratories, media studios, etc., and application of the experience gained there in all higher education institutions of Uzbekistan.

Thirdly, to ensure the solid integration of modern information and communication technologies and educational technologies, to create additional conditions for the continuous development of professional skills of pedagogues in this regard.

Fourth, organizing and conducting courses for teacher training on topics such as the use of interactive presentation systems, the development of interactive and multimedia presentations in connection with the Internet for lectures and seminar classes.

Fifth, to implement the process of distance learning at any time using real-time interactive presentation systems, video conference systems, virtual halls, electronic resources [3].

In particular, the development of the "Electronic Government" system, the increase of the share of electronic public services to 100 percent, the digitization of public services and the transfer of 20 percent of them to the private sector, the introduction of the Mobile ID system for personal identification in the provision of public services, as well as the "Digital Passport of Citizens" and Digital A number of tasks, such as the implementation of "office" projects, are envisaged.

On the basis of public-private partnership, from the establishment of a preschool educational institution to the establishment of activities, receiving subsidies, lending processes have been introduced on the basis of a fully electronic system.

In our opinion, after studying the above practices, it would be expedient to implement the criterion of not less than 40 percent of the

average monthly attendance of children in the allocation of subsidies from the state budget in financing the activities of preschool educational organizations on the basis of public-private partnership.

When the average monthly attendance percentage of preschool education organizations based on public-private partnership and groups of family preschool education organizations is less than 40 percent, wage subsidy is not calculated and paid to employees for the reporting month.

The average monthly attendance of pupils is determined based on the following formula:

$$AMAP = DAP / WDRM$$

In this:

AMAP - average monthly attendance of pupils;

DAP- is the total percentage of daily attendance of pupils during the reporting month. In this case, the daily attendance percentage of pupils is determined by dividing the number of pupils who come to MTT by the number of pupils registered in NMTTBAT on this day and multiplying by 100%;

WDRM- is the number of working days in the reporting month [4].

It serves to ensure effective spending of the funds allocated from the state budget and to improve the financing mechanisms of preschool educational organizations based on public-private partnership.

This operation is carried out in a fully electronic automated system. Through this, it served to ensure effective spending of funds allocated from the state budget and to improve the financing mechanisms of preschool educational organizations based on public-private partnership.

In 2023-2024, respectively, the amount of subsidies allocated for preschool education organizations established on the basis of public-private partnership as part of the total expenses allocated for preschool education from the state budget is as follows:

Fig. 1. The share of PPP subsidies in the total expenditures allocated from the budget for preschool education in 2023-2024, billion som [5].

The table shows that in 2023, the total expenses allocated to preschool education amounted to 10,992 billion som, of which 2,259 billion som or 20.5% correspond to the share of subsidies for preschool education organizations established on the basis of public-private partnerships. It is predicted that in 2024, the total expenses allocated for this sector will increase to 13,507 billion soums, and the amount of subsidies allocated to public-private partnership activities will be 2,892 billion soums or 21.4%.

Subsidies allocated to pre-school education organizations established on the basis of the above public-private partnership include funds allocated from the state budget to cover wages, food and other expenses, 50% of electricity costs and 50% of costs per pupil.

In 2023, preschool education expenditures are planned, taking into account the increase in the coverage of children with preschool education to 72%. By the end of 2025, it is planned to ensure the full coverage of 6-year-old children with the preschool education system and increase the coverage of children to preschool education to 80%.

Based on the decision No. 426 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 2, 2022 “On measures to simplify public-private partnership relations in the field of preschool education with the help

of modern digital technologies”, from September 1, 2022 preschools operating on the basis of public-private partnership In educational organizations, including family non-governmental pre-school education organizations, subsidies from the state budget are determined to be automatically calculated in the Non-State Pre-school Education Organization Management Information System based on the attendance of employees and the attendance of pupils. In this case, the attendance of employees and students is managed using a mobile application through the technology of biometric identification of the person.

As a result of the automatic calculation of the amounts of subsidies and compensations, bureaucratic hassles and red tape in submitting monthly order reports by entrepreneurs have been eliminated.

One of the main tasks of the Public-Private Partnership Development Agency, established under the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is to ensure inter-agency coordination in the implementation of projects in the field of public-private partnership, as well as publicly posting information about projects and maintaining their register. The agency has the right to request information about the implementation, technical-economic and

financial indicators of public-private partnership projects from their initiators and participants [6].

Conclusion and recommendations.

In order to use the advanced foreign experience in the field of digitization in the development of the preschool education system on the basis of public-private partnership in the practice of Uzbekistan, the following measures should be implemented:

1. The following should be considered promising directions of digitalization of the country's education system:

- * providing educational institutions with quality software and information systems that enable the use of information resources;
- * strengthening the requirements for the quality of digital textbooks;
- * introduction of distance technologies

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4. Resolution No. 426 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 2, 2022 "On measures to simplify public-private partnership relations in the field of preschool education with the help of modern digital technologies" stipulates that the following will be regulated.
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6. Resolution PD-3980 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 20, 2018 "On the first measures to create a legal and institutional basis for the development of public-private partnership".

and improvement of the system of evaluation of distance education results;

2. In order to expand the scope of application of digital technologies to the processes of digitization of education, first, it is necessary to simultaneously introduce technical innovations and product innovations into the processes of digital education; secondly, the educational architecture should be comprehensively changed; thirdly, it is necessary to develop methods of using digital technologies based on new professional approaches.

3. It is necessary not to abandon the traditional educational technologies, which have shown their effectiveness, while increasing the accuracy of the assessment of the risks associated with the introduction of innovations into the educational system.